

A Geographical Study of Occupational Structure in Beed District (M.S)

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Abstract:

Occupational structure is major indicators of socio economic development of the any nation. Its varied in and under developed, developing and developed countries in the world. The study of economic development of the people remains incomplete short of its reference to the occupational structure of a population. The aim of the present study is to study and examined occupational structure in the Beed district. Present work is based on the secondary data. According to 2011 census data the proportion of working population of the Beed district was 48.57 percent, most the people engaged in agriculture sector.

Keywords: Work, Worker, Occupation, Labor.

Introduction:

Occupational structure is also known as relatively continuous pattern of the activities that affords workers a livelihood and define their general social status. (Sills, 1968, P. 245). Proportion of persons involved in different types of occupations is a significant economic aspect of population. Occupations are grouped in to three classes viz. i) primary ii) secondary and iii) Tertiary Work has defined as participation in any economically activity with or without compensation, wages or profit. Such participation may be physical or mental in nature. Work involves not only actual work but also includes effective supervision and direction of work. (General Economic Tables, part III, census of India.). India census has classified occupation by four categorized by based on economic activity these are Cultivators, Agriculture labor, household industrial workers

Study Area:

Beed district is located in the middle part of Maharashtra state and extend between 18°27' and 19°27' north latitudes and 74° 49' and 76°44' east longitudes. The east-west distance of Beed district is 268 kms and 127 Km width of the north to south district. Total Geographical area of the district was 10693 sq. kms. and share 3.5 percent area of the Maharashtra state and 19.20 percent area of the Marathwada region. According to the 2011 census figure the total population of Beed district was 2585049 in which total population 1349106 are males and 1235943 are female.

Proportion of Working Population

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and other workers. India is a rural nation of the world most of the people live in rural area and practiced agriculture; hence agriculture is a major economic activity and more than 70 percent people engaged in agriculture sector.

Objective of the study:

- To study and examined occupation structure in the Beed district.
- To study the working structure based on major economic activity in the Beed district.

Database and Methodology:

The present study is based Secondary data. The secondary data has been collected from numerous sources which includes both published and unpublished books, government and private publications. District census handbook, district statistical department, socio economic review and district statistical abstract of Beed district. Collected data is processed and presented in the form of tabular and graphical method.

Table No. 1. Shows the occupational structure of the Beed district. According to 2011 census data the proportion of working population of the study region was 48.57 percent it means more than 50 percent peoples are non-workers.

Table No. 1. Occupational Structure of Beed District: 2011

Tahsil	Total Worker	Cultivators	Agricultural Labor	Household Industrial Workers	Other workers
Ashti	54.38	67.04	19.57	1.44	11.95
Patoda	53.89	63.7	24.41	1.26	10.64
Shirur (Kasar)	55.48	65.97	23.52	1.45	9.05
Georai	53.03	55.21	30.73	1.71	12.34
Manjelgaon	48.52	35.99	45.84	1.36	16.81
Wadwani	51.25	48.74	35.88	1.72	13.66
Beed	43.72	41.24	20.5	1.82	36.44
Kaij	50.53	53.76	31.06	1.95	13.23
Dharur	49.03	41.71	42.05	2.04	14.21
Parli	43.28	33.64	32.23	1.99	32.34
Ambejogai	43.37	35.59	33.39	1.56	29.25
Total District	48.57	48.29	29.74	1.68	20.28

Source: Census Handbook Beed District 2011

At tahsil level the total working population of the study region was not uniformly distributed. The highest working population was observed in Shirur tahsil with 55.48 percent and lowest working population was observed in Parli tahsil. Ashti, Patoda, Shirur, Georai, Wadwani, Kaij and Dharura tahsil recorded above the district average working population while remaining district was recorded below the district average working population. Where the agriculture is a major activity and most of the people engaged in agricultural activity their working population recorded high.

Occupation Structure Based on Major Economic Activity

Working population of Beed district have been classified in four economic categories these are cultivators, agriculture labor, household industrial workers and other workers. The proportion of cultivators, agriculture labor, household industrial workers and other workers were diversely distributed in the study region. Most of the workers engaged in agriculture sector than the other sectors. In year 2011, the proportion of cultivators in the study region was 48.29 percent, highest cultivators was found in Ashti (67.04) and lowest in Parli tahsil (33.64), for the reason that it is an urban area and maximum people involved in other economic activity. Ashti, Patoda, Shirur, Georai, Kaij, and Wadwani tahsil recorded above the regional average cultivators while other tahsils were recorded below the regional average. Agriculture labors is a second most economic activity of study region. According to 2011 census data, the proportion of agriculture labor was 29.74 percent, Highest agricultural labor was found in Majlagaon tahsil and lowest was found in Parli

Tahsil and North Solapur tahsil. Household industry is defined as an industry conducted by one or more members of the household at home or within the rural areas and only within the precincts of the house where the household lives in urban areas (Census of India). In 2011 about 1.69 percent workers was engaged in household industrial sectors. The high house hold workers found in Dharur tahsil followed by Parli and Beed tahsil while, low household industrial was recorded in Patoda and Ashti tahsil. The proportion of other workers in the Beed district was 20.28 percent in 2011. It is a third largest economic sectors of the district. Highest other workers observed in North Parli tahsil followed by Beed and Ambejogai tahsil 2011 census year, due to most of the other workers are found in urban areas than the rural area and Parli Beed and Ambejogai has more urbanized.

Conclusion:

The proportion of total working population of the study region was 48.57 percent. Agriculture

is a major economic activity of the district with more than 80 percent peoples engaged in agriculture sectors. Where the agriculture is dominant economic activity their working population recorded high. Household industrial workers share less account with 1.68 percent and other sectors was 20.28 percent. Agricultural population was recorded high in Ashti, Patoda and Shirur tahsil while high other sectors workers was found in Parli, Beed and Ambejogai

tahsil due to growing market centers and Industrial development in urban city.

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